

PSYCHOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL REFLEX IN FUTURE EDUCATORS

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Annotation. In this article we will talk about the psychological possibilities of increasing the effectiveness of the formation of professional reflex in future educators.

Keywords: reflection, psychologist, metaposition, interiorization, intellektual reflection, personal reflection, communicative reflex, cooperative reflection.

In today's developed age, great attention is paid to the educational process. In the era of rapid development of modern science, technology and Technology, great attention is paid to the educational system and modern psychologists working on it. In our country, serious demands are made on the spiritual appearance, mental potential and professional skills of psychologist personnel.

One of the components of professional competence of a psychologist is professional reflex. Therefore, the effective organization of the educational process of training of psychologists depends on the professional skills of the psychologist.

Reflex (Latin "reflexio" - reversion) - is regarded as the process of cognition of a subject's own (internal) psychological feelings and circumstances. It requires the improvement of the concept of reflection at the level of the requirements of the present time.

Reflection is a form of theoretical activity in which a person, harmoniously developed in all respects, his actions are aimed at understanding their laws, is an activity aimed at self-knowledge and understanding, revealing the specific hidden feelings of the world of spirituality. For the first time, the concept of "reflection" arose in ancient Greek philosophy, which meant that the process of thinking about the thoughts that a person experiences in his consciousness attracts his attention to the analysis of the content of his thoughts. Decart, Socrates, Plato, and other Greek philosophers have argued that reflexion is an activity aimed at recognizing what a person is capable of, what he is capable of. European philosophers, such as Locke, Kant, Hegel, Fikste, Shelling, looked at reflexes as the basis for the development of a person's cognitive abilities.

G.M.Kadzhaspirova believes that "psychological reflection is the self-realization of a person, bunda is not only a psychologist's ability to correctly assess his behavior, but also the ability to understand how the student-student community, pedagogical community, responsible for education, parents, interacting with the psychologist during the dialogue." Therefore, the reflection should be the self-realization of the psychologist, the knowledge, the desire to self-improvement, knowing the pros and cons of the person, to create the necessary conditions for this.

L.E.Pleskach describes the reflex as follows: "reflection is a self-analysis, not the achievement of a self-defined goal, but the acquisition of knowledge, the method of gaining experience, the

stimulation of creativity in relation to professional improvement. On the basis of this theoretical methodological article" the importance of psychological reflection in the development of professional skills of a psychologist " is an indicator of the activities of today's psychologists in the educational process, assessing themselves and making recommendations about their future activities.

In modern psychological research, many scientists rely on the classification of reflection proposed by IN Semyonov. He suggests the following types of reflection

Intellectual reflection - defines positive solutions to problems based on thinking.

Personal reflection - a psychologist's conflict provides a way out of psychological conflicts on the basis of intellectual research.

Communicative reflection is the process by which partners communicate and understand each other.

Cooperative reflection is the activity of coordinating the regular work activities of team members.

The process of self - knowledge takes place at the level of recording information within the psychological skill of the psychologist, the passive form of the bunda reflex takes precedence. The psychologist simply records the causes of various difficulties and problems that arise in his psychological activity, the achievements and results.

The process of self - awareness of the psychologist in relation to his activity and in relation to himself in it standing in the" metaposition " (ambiguous position), looking at oneself from the outside, presupposes the qualification of self-observation. In this, the phenomenon of interiorization (the transition of external factors to internal factors) takes place, the reasons for the occurrence of professional difficulties are formalized; the main goal from activity is determined, the reflex - "I" is formed. This is due to the actual development zone of the psychologist.

In the process of self - determination, the initial level is determined taking into account professional needs and is planned to operate on the basis of intensive opportunities strategic, tactical and operational tasks are formed. True" I "and ideal" I " are proportional. This is due to the degree of development that is closest to the psychologist.

In the process of self - development, the psychological skill of the psychologist, which is improved during professional activity, occurs in the growth of methods and methods of action reflexively (that is, methods that were previously used and became increasingly optimal as a result of assessing their effectiveness).

Self-control refers to the beginning of the second form of self-control, which is based on theoretical and practical experience in the process of the psychologist's activity, further improving his psychological skills by self-professional control.

In our opinion, the constant psychological activity of a psychologist has a reflexive feature of meaning, it covers all reflexive processes. It is worth noting that until now there is no perfect

classification of the concept of psychological reflection. In this regard, it is worth noting that reflection plays an important role in the professional activity of a psychologist.

After all, in the process of professional reflection, the psychologist, to the extent that the chosen psychological profession requires it, compares its capabilities, its existing reflections on it with important aspects of psychological experience, and voluntarily forms a chain of personal psychological skills.

In the work of psychologists G.A. Golisin and G.P. Shedrovsky, reflection is given great importance as a key factor and a natural mechanism for the development of psychological activity of psychologists. G.P. Shedrovsky proposes to study reflection in terms of the "complex of positive activities" of man. He believes that if it is not possible to carry out any psychological activity, the idea is to build a system of "reflexive exit" outside the scope of this activity. In this case, a person moves from the unfulfilled activity, the new activity to the positive policy, and acquires the means of "building meaning", from which he understands and describes the primary activity. In doing so, the second uses the first as an important "material" in the new activity.

This means that a psychologist must be a person who has the professional skills, psychological etiquette, responsibility and duty inherent in psychologists, who objectively fulfills the needs of the psychological process. In this article, we have analyzed the professional skills of the psychologist, his duties to the people, to the Fatherland, his tasks, and reflected on their activities, and decided to make some theoretical, practical and methodological recommendations. Today's psychologists are respected by our people, they are in the public eye. Does the professional pedagogical skills and level of knowledge of today's psychologist satisfy the thirst for knowledge of young people? Today's psychologist has written a synopsis for the daily lesson, moved to an electronic journal and an electronic diary, do these privileges lead psychologists to organize their duties at a high level of competence? We are discussing a number of similar questions with you esteemed colleagues. Inspired by the privileges and opportunities provided, we have many professed psychologists who teach at a high level of diligence and dedication, and our people and government always reflect and reward their services. Setting scientific criteria in the Action Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan: "Further development of the system of continuing education, increasing the capacity of quality educational services, continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in line with modern needs of the labor market" and discussions on the development of science are cross-cutting.

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